

WEAR BEHAVIOUR OF PARTICULATE REINFORCED ALUMINIUM COMPOSITES

D. P. Myriounis, K. Howe, A. McCreadie, S.T.Hasan

Department of Engineering and Mathematics, Sheffield Hallam University, Sheffield, UK

*Corresponding author (d.myriounis@shu.ac.uk)

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1 General Introduction

Aluminium Matrix Composites (AMCs) are now used in braking in most top-level motorsport worldwide, reducing unsprung weight, giving better frictional performance and improved structural properties at high temperatures, compared to cast iron. AMC brakes can withstand temperatures that would make conventional cast iron discs bendable. Reducing mass, especially unsprung, rotating mass at a low cost is a key area of focus. End market applications range from personal vehicles to small, medium and heavy duty vehicles, and even the new E-Bikes and Electric vehicles starting in Europe.

Aluminium based Metal Matrix Composites reinforced with ceramic particles are advanced materials known for their good coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) properties, low cycle fatigue and corrosion fatigue behaviour and high specific strength and wear resistance. Past investigations show that the AMCs have considerable higher wear resistance than conventional cast iron while sliding against automobile friction material under identical conditions [1-2].

In this study the wear behaviour of AMC sliding against automobile friction material was compared with the conventional cast iron. The wear tests carried out on a pin on disc machine, using pin as brake shoe lining material and discs as AMC and

cast iron materials. This test basically involves spinning the disc and applying the pin to its surface to wear it. This is the most common test for research based around wear behaviour in brake discs [3]. This particular test suits brake discs because it matches the real situation of wear in a spinning situation.

Microstructural evidence of the wear behaviour of all samples was observed using Infinite Focus Microscopy (IFM). Infrared (IR) thermography has been employed to measure thermal profiles and heat dissipation variances on the material surfaces during wear testing.

1.1 Wear Mechanisms

When the harder ceramic (SiC) is used at a particular volume fraction as reinforcement to the softer aluminium, they can act together to produce a very useful composite. The reinforcing particles strengthen the softer matrix against plastic deformation thusly easing the problem of high wear rates from the material plastically deforming [4].

The secondary mechanism that helps the wear resistance is that the wear susceptible aluminium is quickly worn down and leaves the ceramic particles protruding from the surface [5]. This leaves the harder particles bearing the brunt of the wear. This is desirable in the case of brake discs because these ceramic particles exhibit better wear resistances, especially when the ductility is improved by the

presence of the ductile aluminium. This produces overall better wear resistance of the composite. The degree of improvement from the reinforcing particles is dependent upon a few factors, such as the hardness of the matrix and reinforcement, the ductility of the matrix, the interfacial cohesion and the volume fraction of the reinforcement. Research by Nakanishi into the development of AMCs as a brake disc showed that the optimal volume fraction content of reinforcing particles is 30%. This is to achieve the best compromise between cost and productivity [6].

Cast iron has functioned well as a brake disc for a number of years however because of the natural density of the material it is very heavy. It has been predicted that the use of an AMC could reduce the weight of the disc brakes by as much as 60% [7]. The thermal managing capability of cast iron lets it down in many ways. The high coefficient of thermal expansion means that as it heats or cools, it expands or contracts to a high degree under repeated cycles causing stress cycles leading to thermal fatigue failures. It has been proven that AMC's tend to have lower coefficients of thermal expansion than cast iron and will therefore not be affected as much by this problem [8-9].

2 Materials

The metal matrix composites studied in this work have been produced by stir casting in the as hot rolled condition and supplied by MC21. Specimens were cut out to perform the tests. The AMCs consisted of aluminium-silicon-magnesium alloy matrix A359, reinforced with silicon carbide particles. Hot rolled A359 Aluminium alloy with 30% SiC particles per volume with an average

particle size of 17 ± 1 μm was used. In Table 1, the chemical composition of the matrix alloy is shown. The microstructure of the examined AMCs in the as-received condition has 2 distinct micro phases as clearly marked on the image micrograph, which are as follows: the aluminium matrix, the SiC particles, (Fig. 1).

Cast iron samples came from a stock part available to buy for a vehicle. Fig. 2a shows the disc brake before machining it into specimens. The pin was made of standard commercially available brake pads material to replicate real braking conditions as much as possible shown in Fig. 2b. Fig. 3a and b shows the Pin (brake pad) and disc (AMC and Cast Iron) respectively.

3 Methodology

3.1 Wear tester

The machine used to perform the wear tests was a CSEM Instrument pin-on-disc wear tester. Figure 4 shows the set up used. The machine is loaded from the top and pushes the pin down onto the surface of the sample. The sample is held by an adjustable holder that is attached to the motor that rotates it. It is controlled by software that calculates sliding distances based on the diameter of the wear scar inputted by the user. The tests were performed at three different loads with three different speeds shown in Table 2.

3.2 Evaluation techniques

3.2.1 Profilometer

The profilometer used was a Veeco DekTak 150. It used a scan range of 65.5 μm , a scan length of 1000 μm and a scan force of 4 mg. The stylus tip was rounded to 12.5 μm , which is smaller than the

expected size of the reinforcing silicon carbide particles. It is important that the top is smaller than the particles to ensure that the profilometer can detect the details of the particles properly. If it were larger than it may not be able to map these areas accurately.

3.2.2 Infinite focus microscope (IFM)

Infinite Focus Microscope was used to inspect the surface profile, check for abnormalities on the surface and measure the surface roughness before and after wear tests, and get the surface texture in 2D and 3D images.

3.2.3 Thermal imaging (IR) camera

Thermal imaging (IR) camera was used (FLIR B400) to monitor heat dissipation profiles during the wear testing. Pictures were taken capturing heat on samples surfaces at five minute intervals. The peak temperatures were ascertained and the distances that it took the samples to reach this peak temperature were noted.

4 Results/Discussions

4.1 Hardness

Hardness testing was carried out prior to wear testing. The hardness results show that the AMC was remarkably softer than the cast iron material (Fig.5) The cast iron samples showed a Vickers hardness of nearly four times more than the AMC.

4.2 Profilometry

The results from the profilometer show the area of material lost from the cross section that was measured. Measurements were taken at 3 different points on the wear track and an average was calculated. This average area loss was then

multiplied by the circumference of the wear track to give an average measurement of the volume lost.

Fig. 6 shows the wear volume loss of both cast iron and AMC. The volume loss of the AMC is much lower than that of the cast iron with the readings taken at 15N for the AMC almost equalling the readings taken at 5N for the cast iron. The difference in wear loss is due to the SiC particles reinforcing the aluminium matrix. These particles are not easily worn and the volume lost could purely be worn carbides have been removed/slide from the matrix instead of being worn down. The surface of the cast iron is worn down much easier and by increasing the applied load volume loss increases, whereas with the AMC this is only a marginal increase in volume loss.

Fig. 7 shows that an increased load gave an increase in the volumetric loss. It shows that the AMC has a shallower gradient with the increasing load than the cast iron does. This proves that the aluminium MMC can deal with the increasing load better than the cast iron and will lose less material, less quickly as the loads increase. It also displays what is expected, that the AMC wore less than the cast iron at the same loads and speeds.

Fig. 8 shows the average values of specific wear rate for cast iron and AMC and it is clearly visible that the cast iron is more prone to wear when compared to the AMC with a constant difference of $1.53 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^3/\text{Nm}$. From the results it can be observed that the wear rate of the AMC is roughly 47% less than that of the cast iron. The behaviour previously mentioned of the wear rate decreasing as the sliding speed increases is now validated as a linear relationship for both materials.

4.3 Infinite Focus Microscope (IFM)

Fig.9a shows the wear tracks created on the cast iron sample and Fig.9b the AMC sample. The images show that the wear scar for the cast iron is more obvious than that on the AMC. To inspect the cast iron wear track further a pseudo colour image was produced with the different colours corresponding to different depths along the surface (Fig.10a, b).

4.4 IR Imaging

It is important to study the thermal capabilities of the material during wear. This means looking at the efficiency of dissipating kinetic energy. During the most extreme case of wear, which occurred at 0.4 m/s and 15 N, a thermal camera recorded the highest temperature rise shown in Figures 11a, b. The results show that the AMC reached a higher surface temperature than the cast iron as shown in Fig.12. The heat was dissipated from the surface and captured by the thermal camera. The results showed that the AMC was able to dissipate more heat at a quicker rate than the cast iron. The added 30% ceramic reinforcement contributes to the heat dissipation mechanism, thus improving the wear behaviour. As the initial wear track is developed there will be more ceramic particles poking through the surface of the aluminium, as the aluminium matrix is quickly worn away. This leaves more ceramic surface area for the heat to disperse from. It is also expected that the aluminium matrix will not expand much more than the cast iron did even with this extra rise in temperature. The lower coefficient of thermal expansion should allow this material to reach higher temperatures and not expand as much. The implications of these results show that the AMC

can function better than the standard brake disc material in terms of slowing the vehicle through the dissipation of kinetic energy as heat. It also helps to show that it will dissipate this energy as heat, instead of through vibration or sound which are both undesirable.

5 Conclusions

On average the particulate reinforced aluminium matrix composite lost 35.6% less volume than the cast iron sample under the same conditions. The average specific wear rate of the aluminium composite was 63.7% less than the cast iron sample. The coefficient of wear was 89.3% less for the aluminium composite than it was for the cast iron.

This concludes that the hard ceramic particles reinforcing the aluminium matrix vastly improves the materials wear resistance. All of the above values conclude that the AMC is more wear resistant than the domestic brake disc.

It was also found that the brake pad transferred more material to the AMC than it did to the cast iron indicating that a harder pad should be used with the AMC discs.

The maximum temperature rise of the AMC sample was nearly 60% more than the cast iron sample. This extra heat could potentially speed up the wear rate of the brake pad. This result supports the above postulations that advanced braking pads are required to deal with this extra heat generated during wear.

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Tables

Material	Elements (wt %)					
	Si	Mg	Mn	Cu	Fe	Zn
A359	9.5	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1

Table 1 Chemical Composition of the Al/SiC_p composite

Loads (N)	5	10	15
Sliding Speed (m/s)	0.3	0.35	0.4

Table 2 Experimental conditions

Figures

Fig. 1. Aluminium/SiC particulate Composite

Fig. 2. Conventional (Cast Iron) Disc brake and commercial phenolic pad

Fig. 3. Pin and disc

Fig. 4. Pin-on-disc wear tester

Fig. 5. Vickers Hardness Test Results

Fig. 6. Wear volume lost vs. Speed for Cast Iron and AMC

Fig. 9. (a) IFM Cast Iron wear track (b) MMC Wear track

Fig. 7. Wear volume lost vs. Load for Cast Iron and AMC

Fig. 8. Average Specific Wear Rate of Cast Iron and Al-MMC

Fig. 10. Cast iron wear scar and in depth roughness analysis using (a) IFM and (b) Profilometry

Fig. 11. Wear Thermal profiles of heat dissipation (speed 0.4m/s, load 15N, distance of 500m) (a) MMC start temp 28.3°C (b) MMC peak at 36.1°C (a) Cast iron start temp at 28.4°C (b) peak temperature at 32.8°C.

Fig. 12. Peak Temperature vs. Applied Force